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*Ideas as More Than Inputs:
Lessons from Sociology and
Art for Inclusive Innovation*

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Executive Summary

This conceptual paper critically examines organisational ideation by comparing traditional management models with sociological theories of creativity, legitimacy, and power. It argues that mainstream innovation processes treat ideas as atomised, value-neutral inputs an approach now accelerated by the increasing use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in idea generation and selection. Drawing on Amabile, Bourdieu, and Becker, the paper explores how AI systems risk reinforcing existing organisational biases and gatekeeping, privileging familiar and historically validated ideas.

In contrast, sociological theory positions ideas as socially constructed artefacts shaped by context, capital, and networks. The paper calls for a shift in innovation theory and practice proposing a more inclusive, reflexive, and ethical approach to ideation. By integrating sociological insights and treating AI as a biased yet useful supporting tool, organisations can design ideation processes that are more equitable and transparent, better suited to complex innovation challenges in diverse and dynamic environments.

Introduction

Ideas sit at the centre of both creativity and innovation but are conceptualised differently across the organisational and sociological disciplines. Organisational theory posits that ideas are cognitive or team-based outputs that must be evaluated, selected, and implemented (Van de Ven, 1986; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Sociological theory contrasts this and views ideas as social artefacts, embedded within networks of meaning, power, and legitimacy (Swidler, 1986; Czarniawska and Joerges, 1996). This paper compares these two traditions to examine how they understand the generation, circulation, and recognition of ideas. This is set against the increasing use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a new actor in ideation processes, one that reflects and potentially reinforces organisational and social biases of its creators (O’Neil, 2016; Noble, 2018). By integrating sociological critique with technological awareness, the paper aims to inform more inclusive and context-sensitive models of ideation.

Ideas in organisational theory

Traditional organisational theory has primarily treated ideas as raw materials and individual elements within a broader innovation process. Amabile’s (1983) componential model defines creativity and, by extension, ideas as the result of domain-relevant skills, creativity-relevant processes, and task motivation. Ideas are seen as the outcome of individual or group-level processes that can be influenced by leadership, culture, and structure. Tidd and Bessant (2014) extend this view by incorporating ideas into a linear innovation model: sensing opportunities, generating ideas, developing solutions, and implementing outcomes. Their model positions ideation as a critical but manageable stage within the

innovation lifecycle. Tools such as suggestion schemes, brainstorming workshops, and digital innovation platforms are presented as mechanisms to harness and manage idea flow (Van de Ven, 1986; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Similar processes, such as the social innovation model (Murray et al., 2010), replicate this linear flow, with ideas a step on the journey.

A key concept that underpins these approaches is the assumption of rationality and control, in line with organisational theory. Ideas are to be evaluated based on their novelty, feasibility, and alignment with organisational goals, as jigsaw pieces that can be put together to create an innovation output (Tidd and Bessant, 2014). Ideation is treated as a cognitive task that can be optimised through training, incentives, and environment design (Amabile, 1996). This approach often resembles a quantum model of creativity: ideas are treated as discrete, context-free units, quanta of novelty to be mined, ranked, and implemented in pursuit of innovation.

This framing is now being extended through the increasing use of Artificial Intelligence in ideation processes, whether to support or even complete the step as part of business innovation. These AI tools are designed to generate, sort, and prioritise ideas at scale, reinforcing the notion that creativity can be automated and systematised (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2020; Wilson and Daugherty, 2018). They deepen the treatment of ideas as measurable, context-independent inputs that can be optimised through data-driven logic.

A further challenge to the approach is that AI systems not only reflect existing organisational priorities but also shape which ideas are surfaced by privileging patterns aligned with prior success or strategic fit (O'Neil, 2016; Noble, 2018). As such, AI becomes an instrument of managerial control, not only accelerating ideation but also potentially narrowing its scope to what is already legible to dominant organisational values. Whether AI can truly be creative and generate unique ideas is yet to be seen (Florida and Goodnight, 2005).

Ideas in Sociological Theory

Approaching the concept of ideas through a sociological lens offers a contrasting view. Sociology rejects the concept that ideas should be treated as isolated atoms of cognitive output. Instead, ideas are situated within broader social, cultural, and institutional systems. Berger and Luckmann (1966) argue that ideas are not generated in a vacuum but are socially constructed through interaction, language, and shared understanding. What we consider a "good" idea is often shaped by existing norms and collective memory.

Bourdieu's field theory (1993) provides further nuance. Within any given field (e.g. academia, art, science), agents compete to have their ideas recognised. However, recognition depends not only on the idea's merit but also on the symbolic capital of its proposer and the alignment with dominant field values. The success of an idea is closely linked to social position rather than solely the inherent qualities of the concept.

This view is extended by Becker (1982), who demonstrated that creative output is always a collective achievement rather than a solo act. A network of connections, from funding partners through to audiences, shapes the viability and meaning of any given idea.

These sociological approaches treat ideas as contested, contextual, and structurally conditioned. Their emergence and uptake are shaped by networks, norms, and inequalities, not simply by individual ingenuity. Nor can they be treated as commodities or neutral raw material within the innovation process (Swidler, 1986; Czarniawska and Joerges, 1996).

Ideas in Art Theory

An alternative viewpoint is that of art theory, which approaches ideas not as measurable units to be selected or implemented but as expressive, emergent, and often non-instrumental constructs. Rather than serving a predefined function, ideas in art frequently exist for exploration, provocation, or emotional resonance (Bourriaud, 2002). Their value lies not in utility but in their capacity to challenge, disrupt, or deepen experience. For instance, conceptual art asserts that “the idea becomes a machine that makes the art” (LeWitt, 1967). This positions the idea itself as the creative act, regardless of whether it leads to a physical product. This reframing removes the obligation for ideas to be practically feasible or outcome-driven, the original form of blue-sky thinking (Travers, 2023).

John Dewey’s (1934) aesthetics treat art as experience, in direct contrast to organisational innovation theory. In this perspective, the process of forming and encountering ideas holds greater importance than the final product. Ideas emerge through experimentation, ambiguity, and iteration rather than through structured development. Failure, contradiction, and absurdity are accepted as integral elements, allowing for a fuller range of creative exploration (Elkins, 2001). None of which are planned for or built into innovation processes.

Ideas within art theory are also said to be shaped by the “distribution of the sensible” (Rancière, 2004). This explores how ideas in art are what is seen, heard, and felt within a given order, underpinned by the bias bound up in them. This further highlights how ideas can be seen as political, by challenging established norms of perception and understanding, something that would be difficult to achieve with gatekeepers protecting hegemonic approaches (Bishop, 2012).

Art theory thus contrasts with organisational models by treating ideas not as tools of productivity but as modes of engagement. It embraces complexity and subjectivity, resisting attempts to streamline ideation into managed, predictable forms (Bourriaud, 2002). This framing allows for more expansive, uncertain, and context-rich understandings of creativity, where meaning is generated rather than extracted (Elkins, 2001). In this sense, ideas in art are lived, not leveraged. This undermines the managerial impulse to optimise ideation and instead frames it as an open-ended, relational process. Art theory thus resists the reduction

of ideas to atomised commodities and restores their experiential, cultural, and affective dimensions. While organisational models prioritise feasibility, alignment, and linear progression, art embraces uncertainty, contradiction, and non-linearity. Ideas in art are valued for their ability to provoke, disrupt, or evoke, not for their efficiency or output potential.

Discussion

This paper has highlighted how ideas are framed in distinctly different ways, across different theoretical approaches. Organisational theory treats ideas as inputs, discrete units to be evaluated, selected, and implemented within managed innovation systems. In contrast, sociological theory views ideas as socially constructed artefacts, shaped by power, legitimacy, and positionality. Art theory departs further, framing ideas as aesthetic experiences, often ambiguous, emotional, and not intended for utility or resolution. These divergent framings reveal core tensions.

Organisational approaches seek clarity, control, and output, whereas both sociology and art foreground ambiguity, context, and emergence. While managerial models demand objective assessment and strategic alignment, sociological and artistic perspectives reveal that ideas are relational, shaped by networks, institutions, and the emotions of those who produce and interpret them.

Adopting a singular view such as organisational innovation theory, removes the diversity and complexity of ideas, substituting it instead for an easy to manage stage that create atomised inputs into a process. The organisational theory approach to ideas also creates limitations in practice. The assumption that ideas are transferable and context-independent, overlooking how meaning is shaped by cultural and institutional settings leads to the privileging of dominant voices, as organisational gatekeeping often excludes alternative or marginal perspectives.

By focusing on ideas solely for their instrumental value, measured by strategic fit or commercial potential, it offers a barrier to creativity and discourages open-ended exploration. As a result, ideation becomes a narrow, efficiency-driven exercise, marginalising critical, emotional, or socially grounded contributions that may offer greater long-term value and insight within complex organisational environments. This in turn leads to innovation becoming a closed system, efficient but impoverished, where socially, emotionally, or politically grounded ideas are sidelined.

This paper argues for a reframing of ideation as a socially embedded process, with ideas being seen as situated constructs shaped by who creates them, where they emerge, and under what conditions they are legitimised. Drawing from sociology and art, this perspective challenges dominant ideation models and advocates for pluralism, reflexivity, and contextual innovation. Therefore, a more critical and inclusive model is needed, one

that addresses the challenges of an industrialised, linear innovation process, where ideas are treated as atomised inputs. It will need to integrating insights from sociology and art, deviating from the dominance of efficiency-driven ideation models and highlights the value of pluralism, reflexivity, and disruption. To foster meaningful innovation, organisations must reframe ideation as a socially embedded process, open to ambiguity, contestation, and alternative forms of value beyond commercial metrics or managerial convenience.

Areas for further research

Power and Legitimacy in Organisational Ideation

Future research could explore how organisational structures, and cultural hierarchies influence which ideas are surfaced, legitimised, or suppressed. This includes examining whose voices are heard in innovation processes and how power dynamics shape idea recognition across different sectors and contexts.

Comparative Studies of Ideation Practices

A comparative analysis of ideation practices across domains—such as corporate settings, grassroots movements, and artistic collectives—could illuminate how different environments foster, interpret, and value ideas. This would support a more nuanced understanding of ideation beyond standardised innovation models.

Reframing Idea Evaluation Metrics

Research is needed to develop alternative frameworks for assessing ideas that go beyond feasibility and novelty. This might include criteria rooted in cultural resonance, emotional impact, social legitimacy, or ethical considerations, especially in relation to marginalised or underrepresented groups.

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